

PRIOR KNOWLEDGE AS AN ENABLER OF ADDITIVE MANUFACTURING TECHNOLOGIES

Abstract

Additive manufacturing technology is often considered as a key technology with disruptive potential. This article researches the relationship between the use of different additive technology applications (rapid prototyping and additive manufacturing) and product innovation. More specifically, we focus on the question to what extent characteristics of the firm's prior knowledge support the adoption of additive manufacturing technologies for product innovation. Theoretically, the depth and scope of firms' prior knowledge including prior experience, readiness, resources, the nature and scale of the organization, the amount invested, and external environmental aspects, represent a strategic resource for the successful adoption of additive technology. Utilizing a large-scale quantitative dataset of 3,180 European manufacturing firms from 2015, descriptive and multivariate analyses confirm the positive relationship between firms' adoption of additive technology and product innovation. This study enriches knowledge of how firms' strategic resource endowment affects the adoption of additive technology for product innovation. Our findings underline the relevance to build and prepare the firm with prior knowledge relevant for technology adoption of additive manufacturing technology.

Keywords: additive manufacturing, 3D printing, innovation, knowledge, digitalization, digital innovation

INTRODUCTION

The role of new digital technologies for innovation have thus far received little attention in research, which is a gap noted in recent articles (Candi and Beltagui 2019; Lanzolla, Pesce, and Tucci 2021; Zhao et al. 2021). With the advent of digital technologies, products and services can be updated and launched with new connectivity capabilities and new business models can be adopted. Industry 4.0, augmented reality, sensor technologies, and additive manufacturing enable an almost endless set of new opportunities, which potentially have significant commercial impact (Öberg, Shams, and Asnafi 2018; Piller, Weller, and Kleer 2015; Savolainen and Collan 2020). While the research stream is young it has already bifurcated into two separate yet connected research streams of digital transformation and digital innovation (Appio et al. 2021; Wetzels 2021).

One of the technologies that yield the highest digital transformative potential is additive manufacturing technology (henceforth AMT) (Savolainen and Collan 2020; Rindfleisch, O'Hern, and Sachdev 2017). AMT enables the development and production of three-dimensional objects by adding material in a layer-by-layer fashion, which distinguishes additive manufacturing fundamentally from traditional processes using forming and subtractive techniques like pressing, molding or machining. Just like artificial intelligence, AMT may not only be considered a technical process innovation, but even an *invention of a method of invention* (Cockburn, Henderson, & Stern, 2017). Expectations regarding AMT are high, especially for product development (Candi & Beltagui, 2019; Ren et al., 2018; Srinivasana et al., 2018). While there is a rich and growing body of literature dealing with different antecedents and conditions of successful adoption of digital technologies e.g., business models (Weiking et al. 2020), business ecosystems (Skylar et al. 2019), dynamic capabilities (Coreynen, Matthyssens, and Van Bockhaven 2017),

external relationships (Grandinetti et al. 2020), customization ability (Kohtamäki et al. 2020), or sustainability orientation (Zhao et al., 2021; Niaki et al., 2019), the role of firms' past experience and knowledge base has been underestimated to date (Paiola et al. 2021; Rosenzweig and Mazursky 2014). For instance, in their recent study, Candi and Beltagui (2019) deploying survey data from 177 US firms show that the use of AMT can have positive effects on firms' innovation performance, if companies manage to orchestrate the functions involved in its implementation and use. This highlights the need for additional research on the question, *how* companies resource base is linked to their use of novel technologies like AMT.

To investigate this research gap, this article deploys a knowledge-based view (KBV) of the firm to develop a conceptual framework explaining how firms identify, endow, and exploit prior knowledge to adopt and take advantage of new digital technology (Brinckmann and Hoegl 2011; Wu 2007; Camisón-Haba, Clemente-Almendros, and Gonzalez-Cruz 2019). As Herschbach (1995: 31) has put it, *technology is organized knowledge for practical purposes*. The theory behind this view dates back to Cohen and Levinthal (1990) where they argue that prior knowledge has a decisive influence on absorptive capacity, which in turn has an effect on a firm's capacity for innovation and technology adoption. Hence, not only is the search and selection of new technologies crucial for firms' future performance; it is equally important to build prior technological knowledge to benefit from such technologies. Specifically, in the context of AMT, we argue that different characteristics of a firm's prior knowledge base relate to the successful adoption of the AMT, which in turn influences a firm's capacity and success with innovation.

Consequently, the underlying research question of this article is:

To what extent do characteristics of the firm's prior knowledge support the adoption of additive manufacturing technologies for product innovation?

The article makes the following contributions based on a large-scale quantitative dataset of European manufacturing firms. The results adds theoretical insights of different characteristics of prior knowledge of firms to current theorizing in innovation management on digital innovation and to models of technology acceptance and adoption (Venkatesh and Davis 2000). The empirical results highlight the importance of using AMT both for rapid prototyping and for additive manufacturing purposes, and when using AMT for both purposes for obtaining incremental as well as radical innovation. In contrast to the perspectives discussed by Rindfleisch, O'Hern, and Sachdev (2017), we do confirm a positive relationship between adoption of AMT and innovation. Therefore, the studies makes an empirical contribution to the literature on the adoption of AMT, which according to Zhao et al. (2020) and Niaki, Torabi, and Nonino (2019) has been largely conceptual in nature. Theoretically, the results show the importance of both depth and scope of firms' prior knowledge for the adoption of AMT. More specifically, while a higher share of tertiary educated employees benefit innovation and radical innovation, it is the staff with secondary upper education that support the adoption of AMT. These results highlight the importance for firms in creating and maintain the right mix of skills for digital technology adoption and innovation. The depth of the knowledge base is further important for both innovation and adoption of AMT when seen through the lens of R&D. Hence, this research thereby both adds to and deepens the current understanding of the role of prior knowledge as an antecedent of digital technology adoption and thus thereby enriches the Knowledge-based view of the firm (KBV) as well as current innovation management research.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

AMT holds tremendous potential for unfolding new creative opportunities and innovation endeavors (Khorram Niaki and Nonino 2016; Rayna, Striukova, and Darlington 2015). Meanwhile, AMT have reached a technical maturity level which justify the categorization of AMT as a new paradigm of manufacturing (Som et al. 2016; Steenhuis and Pretorius 2017). In this way, AMT may deliver physical objects and, at the same time, draw on and create data for new innovative ventures, the very nature of digital innovation.

AMT and Innovation

The new freedom in design and the increasing cost-effectiveness of small series and one-off productions led Hopkinson et al. (2006) to diagnose a disruptive potential of AMT early on, although Savolainen and Collan (2020) argue that this depends on the business environment and the presence of complementary organizational process assets in the firm. Organizational process assets contain on the one hand applied processes and procedures and on the other hand the corporate knowledge base (PMI 2013; Institute 2013). This includes artifacts, practice and/or knowledge to perform a specific task. Furthermore, the corporate knowledge base includes process management databases on processes and products itself (PMI 2013) which links therefore the gained knowledge in AMT to the corporate assets. Thus, AMT does not tie with the existing body of knowledge of conventional manufacturing processes but are based on a completely new approach to the development and production of goods in terms of their basic and effective principles. Previous literature has revealed that AMT opens the doors for new types of innovation in product development and product engineering. For instance, Floriane et al. (2016) showed that AMT enhances the design process of new products by allowing for quick experiments and trials with different product designs. Likewise, AMT enables new functional product designs (Perez et al. 2019; Petrovic et al. 2010) as well as new options for sustainable

product design (Sauerwein et al. 2019; Gebler, Schoot Uiterkamp, and Visser 2014). Furthermore, the use of AMT can unlock inventors' and engineers' creativity by offering new possibilities for realizing complex geometrical shapes that could not be implemented by conventional manufacturing technologies in the past (Mawale, Kuthe, and Dahake 2016). Furthermore, additive technologies can contribute to reduce the time-to-market of new products (Appio et al. 2021; Gibson, Rosen, and Stucker 2010), increase opportunities for product co-design and co-creation with customers and end-users (Rindfleisch, O'Hern, and Sachdev 2017; Nickerson 2015). Hence, the use of new technological devices represents a major source of advantage for innovating companies in terms of incremental and radical product innovation (Rosenzweig and Mazursky 2014). Based on survey data from 177 US firms, Candi and Beltagui (2019) showed that the use of AMT can have a positive effect on firms' innovation performance under certain external and internal frame conditions.

H1: The adoption of AMT positively relates to firms' product innovation.

Firms' prior knowledge base as an antecedent of AMT adoption

Sousa-Zomer, Neely, and Martinez (2020) as well as Ghosh et al. (2022) identified certain core capabilities building the foundation for companies' digital transformative capability along the dimensions of digital sensing, digital seizing, and digital reconfiguration. Thus, the adoption of new technologies is not determined solely by specific technological characteristics, but also by further organizational prerequisites of companies (Kinkel, Baumgartner, and Cherubini 2022). According to the technology adoption theory the successful adoption of technology depends both on both individual characteristics and internal and external characteristics of the organization (Ukobitz and Faullant 2022).

While most models like the technology acceptance model (TAM), theory of reasoned action (TRA) or theory of planned behavior (TPB) focus on individual's attitude and behavior towards new technology, the Technology-Organization-Environment (TOE) framework by Tornatzky and Fleischer (1990) focusses on organizational-level factors to explain successful technology adoption such as technological, organizational, and environmental frame conditions (Baker 2011).

The proponents of the knowledge-based view regard firms as organizational entities operating based on repositories of distinct productive (technological and organizational) knowledge to learn and grow based on this knowledge (Grant 1996b, 1996a; Liebeskind 1996; Spender 1996; Szulanski 1996). The concept of prior knowledge originates in the seminal concept of absorptive capacity (Cohen and Levinthal 1990). Generally, prior knowledge includes a firm's prior experience, readiness, resources, infrastructure, and business environment, as well as the nature and scale of the organization, the amount invested, and external environmental aspects (Paiola et al. 2021) which can play a decisive role for the firm's ability to source, adopt, implement, and exploit new external knowledge (e.g., new technologies) to commercial ends. Thus, prior knowledge has a decisive influence on absorptive capacity, which in turn strongly affects a firm's capacity for innovation (Paiola et al. 2021). It is more efficient for firms to build on and integrate prior internal knowledge that organizational members already know than to access new external knowledge and integrate it with internal knowledge (Grant 1997; Kogut and Zander 1992).

Due to the character of digital technologies in general, and AMT in particular, the adoption comes along with a wide variety of possible applications and innovation impulses for products and processes showing strong complementarities with existing or potential new technological knowledge (Ennen and Richter 2010; Schmiedeberg 2008).

For instance, Cattani (2006) provides evidence that firms' prior knowledge can become valuable and be re-deployed in a different domain during technological development. Likewise, Tanaka and Masuda (2020) show that business organizations should prepare and accumulate knowledge long before business change is expected by means of a pre-adaptation strategy as a complement to R&D and other search strategies for new technologies. Building on the concept of *exaptation* (Mastrogiorgio and Gilsing 2016), Andriani and Kaminska (2021) suggests that the exaptive method of discovery involves novelty emerging from new uses of existing technologies and materials. Finally, Khanzode et al. (2021) argued that the non-preparedness of the workforce as well as missing knowledge about digital technologies are among the major barriers to Industry 4.0 technology adoption by small and medium sized companies. Given this rather fragmented research landscape, Paiola et al. (2021) conclude from the literature review, there is still a paucity of systematic research on the importance of prior knowledge to the adoption of I4.0 technologies. We follow the previous work by Oliveira and Martin (2011) and Kinkel et al. (2022) by applying the TOE framework for analyzing the adoption of AMT with an explicit focus on the firm's prior knowledge on the technological, organizational, and environmental level.

Prior knowledge on the technological level

As mentioned above, manufacturing firms can apply AMT for multiple purposes in different functional areas like product development, engineering, production, or services and aftersales (e.g., production of spare parts) (Gibson, 2017). Being based on digitally layered 3D-models of products, AM belongs to the family of digital manufacturing technologies (Holmström et al., 2016) and is often considered as one of the core technologies of "Industry 4.0/Smart Factory" (Wan, Cai, & Zhou, 2015). Being one of Industry's 4.0 digital core technologies (Wan, Cai, and Zhou 2015) AMT need to be

embedded into a digital environment comprehending digital document management systems, CAD-CAM systems for designing, engineering, and executing the manufacturing of digital 3D-layered models (Holmström et al. 2016).

When implementing digital manufacturing technologies such as AMT, firms face major changes. These changes mainly refer to the integration of digital networks and technologies across multiple areas within the organization, but also digitalization of elements such as physical objects, human actors, intelligent machines, production lines, as well as processes, to create digital ecosystems (Geissbauer, Vedso, and Schrauf 2016; Klötzer and Pflaum 2017; Schumacher, Erol, and Sihm 2016). In terms of prior knowledge, we thus argue that the adoption of AMT benefits from the given digital maturity of the firm. The term “digital maturity” is interpreted in two distinct ways (Chanas and Hess 2016). On the one hand, from a technological point of view, it can refer to the definition of digitization. It thereby represents the digital information flow and the use of information technologies within a company (Chanas and Hess 2016; Klötzer and Pflaum 2017). On the other hand, the management perspective suggests a definition according to *the status of a company’s digital transformation* (Chanas and Hess 2016, p. 4). This includes an assessment of past activities that can be attributed to the effort of transformation and their resulting improvements in an operational context as well as in leading the internal change process (Chanas and Hess 2016). A digitally mature firm is defined by taking three aspects into consideration: (1) horizontal integration, (2) vertical integration, and (3) end-to-end engineering integration (Salkin et al. 2017; Scremin et al. 2018; Wang et al. 2016; Lee et al. 2017). To create automatized information flows and efficient ecosystems, horizontal integration is achieved through technology integrations across different functional areas and different value-creating processes within the firm. Vertical integration refers to creating transparent processes and networked self-organized

systems through cross-linking and digitalization of hierarchical business units, enabling flexible and adaptive systems and communication. Finally, end-to-end digital engineering integration is achieved through technological integrations across processes and products to achieve seamless connections between the digital and physical world. Together these aspects enable real time data sharing, efficient resource allocation, as well as interconnected business units (Salkin et al. 2017).

Prior knowledge influences technology adoption by enriching the firms' knowledge stock and additionally improves firms' recombination capabilities to solve problems (Leiponen and Helfat 2009). The more knowledge recently integrated into firms' internal knowledge stock, the more likely they are to develop knowledge integrating mechanisms and intra-organizational coordination necessary to adopt AMT successfully (Caner and Tyler 2015; Grant 1996b, 1996a). As Caner and Tylor (2015, p. 811) summarize, *these newly established integration mechanisms enhance the level of common knowledge, the frequency and variability of task performance, and organization structure.*

Because manufacturing firms can apply additive technologies for multiple purposes in different functional areas like product development, engineering, production, or services and aftersales (e.g., production of spare parts) (Gibson 2017), we argue that firms have an advantage in adopting AMT when they can build on previous use and experience with other digital technologies. Thus, AMT adoption would benefit from complementarities arising from digital maturity of the firm. Hence, we can derive the following hypothesis:

H2: Firms with higher digital maturity have a higher propensity to adopt AMT.

Prior knowledge on the organizational level

Innovating requires knowledge depth, which refers to the degree to which firms can reuse their available internal knowledge repeatedly (Katila and Ahuja 2002). The depth of firms'

prior knowledge base can equally emerge from stocks of explicit and tacit knowledge available on the individual and organizational level (Nonaka and Takeuchi, 1995).

On the individual level, formal education of employees is essentially forming their knowledge about subject matter, methods, and application. This knowledge base delineates the domain within which an individual can improve his understanding of what he knows, and from which he develops solutions, manages time and resources, and monitors results (Knudsen and Schleimer 2022). Moreover, formal education provides knowledge that strongly influences a person's cognitive reasoning skills and reflects their cognitive abilities (Amabile 1988; Hambrick and Mason 1984). Employees with graduate and PhD-degrees as well as qualified skilled workers hold a high level of domain-specific knowledge. Employees with higher levels of education have more depth allowing them to produce novel and creative outcomes as they apply their stronger cognitive abilities and methodological expertise to domain specific problems (Bantel and Jackson 1989; Kimberly and Evanisko 1981). A higher level of education also enables the individual to store and use prior knowledge in the knowledge domain more extensively, than it would be the case for an individual with the same or a lower level of education (McDonough 1993). Finally, higher levels of education result in a higher absorptive capacity within the knowledge domain (Cohen and Levinthal 1990; Nieves, Quintana, and Osorio 2016). Therefore, employees' prior knowledge base obtained through formal education is an absorptive capability that can, for instance in the context of technology adoption, lead to a value-adding outcome for the company (Schleimer and Pedersen 2013; Horvat, Dreher, and Som 2019).

On the organizational level, the depth of prior knowledge is reflected by the performance of internal R&D. According to the Frascati-Manual (OECD 2002), R&D represents the institutionalized, systematic search and generation of new knowledge to problems when

the solution is not readily apparent to someone familiar with the basic stock of commonly used knowledge and techniques within the firm. The term “systematic” thereby refers to the use of processual aspects of scientific regularities, the use of scientific methods, the intersubjectivity of the applied methodology, and the logical consistency (in terms of objectivity, reliability, and validity) (Godin 2001).

As argued above, AMT is not necessarily in tie with the existing body of prior knowledge of conventional processes. Instead, it might constitute a completely new approach to the development and production of goods. Accordingly, AMT can be assumed to have a wider impact, for example, on the organizational processes, the nature of work, required skills, the way of communication and collaboration, leadership, openness of product development (Petrulia 2020; Marion and Fixson 2020). Thus, the successful adoption of AMT is dependent upon the firms’ ability to generate and internalize new knowledge and to integrate this with its prior knowledge base. Consequently, we assume that firms’ knowledge depth in terms of prior explicit knowledge – whether at the individual or organizational level - positively influences the adoption of AMT.

H3: Firms with a more prior knowledge on the organizational level have a higher propensity to adopt AMT.

RESEARCH DESIGN

The analysis utilizes data from the European Manufacturing Survey (EMS), a cross-European survey of manufacturing firms. The EMS focuses on topics such as technical modernization, the introduction of new organizational concepts, or product and service innovation, and several control variables. Information gathered in the EMS is based on self-assessments of the respondent, for example if they consider a new product to be a market novelty or not. There is a discussion if self-assessments by firms are viable data

for econometric studies of innovation (Mairesse and Mohnen 2010), but this kind of indicators is widely used. To ensure for methodological rigor and comparability, all innovation indicators used in the EMS are in line with the recommendations of the OSLO Manual (OECD, 2018) which represents the methodological guideline for the European Community Innovation Survey (CIS).

This article employs the 2015 wave of EMS covering the years 2012-2015. It includes 3,180 manufacturing firms with at least 20 employees from Germany, Austria, Denmark, Switzerland, the Netherlands, Spain, Slovenia, Croatia and Serbia. Germany is the country with the largest number of observations in the sample (1,174), followed by Switzerland (706), Serbia (278), Denmark (245) and Austria (214). All countries used the same questionnaire that was translated into national languages (and back-translated to ensure a coherent multi-language survey), pre-tested, and collected by the national teams. Some used online survey tools, others article and pencil surveys, and all carried out the data collection in the exact same period of time and with the same survey process. Table 1 provides a description of all dependent and independent variables used for the analyses, including their abbreviation, mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum value.

-Table 1 -

AMT for rapid prototyping and additive manufacturing

The EMS operationalizes the adoption of AMT by two different questions: one asks if the firm uses AMT to produce prototypes (rapid prototyping), the second asks about the use of AMT for manufacturing purposes. To make sure that all respondents have a common understanding of AMT, the survey lists Fused Deposition Modelling (FDM), Selective Laser Sintering (SLS), Stereolithography (SLT), Selective Laser Melting (SLM), and

Electron Beam Based method (EBM) technologies as examples of AMT. We construct four variables based on these questions:

1. “*AMT*” equals 1, if the firm uses any type of AMT, otherwise 0
2. “*only_p*” equals 1, if the firm uses AMT only for rapid prototyping, and otherwise 0
3. “*only_m*” equals 1 if the firm uses AMT only for manufacturing, and otherwise 0;
4. “*both*” equals 1 if the firm employs both types of AMT, and otherwise 0.

Consequently, all four variables equal 0 for firms that do not use any type of AMT.

The data set also provides information about the year in which firms have adopted AMT for the first time. To account for the time lag between the year of first AMT adoption and product innovation, we exclude those cases (n=154) that have introduced AMT later than 2012. Thereby, we can make sure, that relationship between AMT and firms’ product innovation can only show unidirectional effects. We do not intend to talk about causality here, but merely ensure that technologies have been in fact adopted before the product innovation intensity is observed.

Characteristics of prior knowledge

The *prior organisational knowledge* on the *individual level* is operationalized by the formal education structure of the employees (Da Silva & Davis, 2011; Knudsen & Schleimer, 2020). We use the percentages of employees holding a tertiary degree (*skill_1*) and employees with upper-secondary education or equivalent vocational training (*skill_2*). Mean, standard deviation, maximal and minimum value for these two variables can be found in Table 1. On the *organizational level*, depth of prior knowledge is measured a question which asks if the firm is active in R&D. The variable “*RD*” equals 1 if the firm does R&D, and 0 otherwise.

Prior knowledge on the technological level

The prior technological knowledge influences technology adoption by enriching the firms' knowledge stock and additionally improves firms' recombination capabilities to solve problems (Leiponen and Helfat 2009). To measure the scope of prior knowledge related to the use of digital technologies, we use the concept of digital maturity. Digital maturity in its technical understanding refers to the existing levels of digital information flows as well as the use of digital information and manufacturing technologies within a company (Chanas and Hess 2016; Klötzer and Pflaum 2017). We measure the degree of digital maturity by an index that includes six digital technologies (software for production planning and scheduling, digital exchange of product/process data with suppliers/customers, near real-time production control systems, product-lifecycle-management-systems, virtual reality or simulation for product design or product development, and mobile/wireless devices for programming and controlling). The index (*digindex*) is calculated as suggested by Lerch, Jäger, and Maloca (2017) and cumulatively increases with the number and sophistication of the six digital technologies used on a five-items scale.

As the scope of prior knowledge also refers to the use of firm-external knowledge sources (Craner & Tyler, 2015), we deploy two additional variables. The first one (*s_cus*) equals 1 if firms use customers as an external source of innovation knowledge, and 0 otherwise. The second one (*s_sup*) equals 1 if firms receive external innovation knowledge from their suppliers, and zero otherwise.

Product innovation

The dependent variable in the first set of regressions is product innovation, that is, if the firm has introduced a new or significantly improved product to the market between 2012 and 2015. This variable is based on the definition provided in the OSLO manual (OECD

2018). We use two variants of the variable: first, a binary variable (*innov*) that is 1 if the firm has introduced a new product, and 0 otherwise. Second, with the aim to capture different degrees of innovativeness, we introduce a variable that measures radical innovation (*radical*). A radical innovation is a product new to the market, not just new to the firm. It is implemented in an ordinal variable (*radical*) that is 1 if the firm has introduced a radical innovation, and 0 otherwise.

Control variables

Control variables include first a control for the competitiveness of the firm. We have used the export share (percentage) of the firm to total turnover (*export*) as a measure of sophistication in the market orientation of the firms. Second, we control for the firm's market in terms of either being business-to-consumer or business-to-business. The variable *consumer* takes the value of 1 if the firm's main line of products is oriented towards being a producer of finished products towards consumer markets (as an alternative to finished products towards industrial customers, a supplier or a contract manufacturer). Further, a standard control is included for firm size measured by the logarithm of the number of employees (*lemp*). Industry affiliation is aggregated for industries at the NACE 2 digits level into 12 groups and these are included as industry dummies with the food and beverage industry (*fb*) as reference. Finally, we add dummy variables for the eight countries with Germany as the reference category to account for national differences in AMT use.

The multivariate analysis employs probit regression with *innov* and *radical* and for the adoption of *only_p*, *only_m*, and *both* as the dependent variables.

DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

The diffusion of AMT started quite slowly with first applications in the firms of the

sample in the mid-1990s accelerated markedly after the year 2010 with growing capabilities of the technology (*Figure 1*). Around 2015, however, adoption rates of AMT are still low with around 88% of the firms not having adopted the technology (*Table 2*).

-Figure 1-

AMT is more frequently adopted for manufacturing purposes than for rapid prototyping (RP) (4.7 vs. 5 percent), while 2.6 percent of all firms use AMT for both applications (*Table 2*, column 1). Around 12% of all firms in the sample use one or both types of AMT. RP, however, only became popular in the years after 2010 and has been growing faster in the last years, while additive manufacturing is the technology that has been used for the longest. This can be seen from the second column of *Table 2* which reports the average number of years of use for each type of AMT. Some firms with additive manufacturing even made their first investments before 1980, and a third of the firms before the year 2000. Shorter average experience with rapid prototyping also implies a faster diffusion of this AMT application given that the share of firms who use both variants is almost equal. This may be explained by smaller, less expensive printers.

- Table 2 -

A second striking difference between firms that use additive manufacturing and those that use rapid prototyping is firm size. The average user of rapid prototyping is four times larger than a firm that only uses additive manufacturing (*Table 2*, column 2). Altogether, firms that use AMT are larger than firms that do not use AMT. There is also a noticeable difference between adopters and non-adopters of AMT in the share of high-skilled employees (*Table 2*, column 4). Differences in the skills structure within the group of AMT adaptors, in contrast, are very small. There is also only a slight difference in the intensity firms use impulses from customers as an input for the development of new

products (*Table 2*, last column).

We further investigate the relationship between firm size and AMT adoption in *Table 3* which shows the share of firms that have adopted AMT across four size classes. The adoption of AMT markedly increases with firm size for rapid prototyping, whereas for additive manufacturing the share of users is the same across the size groups. This suggests that large firms have adopted rapid prototyping recently as a ‘nice-to-have’ for experimentation, as 3D printers have become less expensive over the past years. Additive manufacturing, in contrast, may be essential for a certain type of firms across different size categories.

- *Table 3* -

Investments in AMT are also highly sector-specific (*Table 4*). In food and beverages or the textiles and clothing industry, hardly any firms have adopted AMT. This may be due to the manufacturing process in these sectors as well as the rather low maturity of available AMT solutions for these sectors. The highest share of AMT adopters is found in the computer and the electrical industry, where AMT is more frequently used for rapid prototyping. In contrast, additive manufacturing is much more evenly distributed among the sectors.

- *Table 4* -

Descriptive statistics also show a positive relationship between AMT and innovation at the firm level (*Table 5*, first column). The share of product innovators is larger among users of AMT, irrespective of the purpose of use compared to firms that do not use AMT. The share of innovators is higher among users of rapid prototyping application as well as among simultaneous users of both AMT applications compared to users of additive manufacturing applications. However, contrary to popular opinion, AMT does not reduce

time-to-market from the product idea to market introduction: on average, time-to-market is even five months longer for users of rapid prototyping compared to firms with no AMT (*Table 5*, column 2). The third column offers one possible explanation to this finding: firms using AMT more often aspire for products that are new to the market (radical innovations) than firms with no AMT (*Table 5*, column 3). A similar pattern can be found among firms with R&D activities. 75% of all firms with rapid prototyping also perform R&D activities (*Table 5*, column 4).

- Table 5 -

MULTIVARIATE RESULTS

Descriptive statistics are important to gain insights into fundamental relationships between the variables, but do not account for relationships between several variables simultaneously. Thus, we employ probit regression to investigate these relationships in a multivariate set-up. The variables used in the regression have been described above and are listed in Table 1.

We first we investigate the relationship between AMT and product innovation. *Hypothesis H1* assumes a positive relationship between innovation and AMT. The dependent variable in column 1 of Table 6 is *innov*, which is 1 if the firm has introduced a new product, and 0 otherwise. Column 2 in Table 6 further elaborates the analysis by introducing market novelties as a form of radical innovation. Here, innovation performance is measured by dummy variable (*radical*) that is 1 if the firm has introduced a market novelty past three years, and 0 otherwise.

Independent variables distinguish between firms that solely use rapid prototyping (*only_p*), firms that solely use additive manufacturing (*only_m*), and firms that employ both forms of AMT (*both*). The base case is no AMT use. Results for all three types of

AMT support *Hypothesis 1*: firms that have adopted AM are more likely to be innovative than firms without AMT, all other factors equal. The likelihood of a product innovation increases by around 14% if the firm uses both types of AMT and by more than 18% in the case of radical innovation compared to firms with no AMT. The coefficients for the sole use of rapid prototyping and additive manufacturing are also positive and significant, but smaller. This indicates that the positive association between AMT and innovation is largest when the firm employs both types of AMT in parallel.

Various forms of knowledge, such as R&D (*RD*), skills (*skill_1* and *skill_2*), or digitalization (*digindex*) reveal the expected positive relationship to innovation. Moreover, we find support for a positive relationship between the status of the firm and being a producer of consumer goods only for innovation, not for radical innovation. Exports have a positive relationship to innovation, as expected, however the coefficient is very small.

- Table 6 -

In a second step, to test *Hypothesis 2* which states that digital maturity is positively related to AMT, we include an index of digitalization (*digindex*) which was described above. The diffusion of AMT in general and rapid prototyping benefits from a high digital maturity (*digindex*) in the firm in terms of prior technological knowledge. Interestingly..., but this is not the case for additive manufacturing. Thus, *Hypothesis 2* is supported for AMT in general and rapid prototyping, but not for additive manufacturing.

Thirdly, we look at the determinants of AMT adoption and its relationship to the prior knowledge base of firms (*Table 7*). *Hypothesis 3* assumes that firms with a higher depth of prior knowledge on both the individual and organisational level have a higher propensity to adopt AMT. To test this association, we first include variables for knowledge from education (*skill_1* and *skill_2*) and knowledge from R&D (*RD*) in both

regressions.

- Table 7 -

The results support *Hypothesis 3* in general, but also show some differences between AMTs. *Hypothesis 3* is supported for AMT in general (*Table 7*, column 1), and rapid prototyping (*Table 7*, column 2), but not for additive manufacturing (*Table 7*, column 3) which does not reveal a positive association with R&D, and a positive relationship with *skills_2* sets only at the error level of 10% and less. It should also be noted that the share of staff with tertiary education is irrelevant for the adoption of AMTs; its the share of people with upper secondary education that counts, so people who are working in production rather than design or R&D.

Regression results also confirm that AMT is associated with rising firm size. However, we find considerable differences between the results for AMT, rapid prototyping, and additive manufacturing. The latter is negatively associated with firm size, so it is a technology that is found small firms, which confirms the results from *Table 4*. The manufacturers of rubber and plastic products, computers, electrical equipment, vehicles and other products reveal the highest differences in the adoption of AMT compared to the base case, the food and beverages industry, so AMT is more frequently found in high-tech industries. This, however, cannot be confirmed for additive manufacturing.

A surprising result from the regression are the differences between rapid prototyping and additive manufacturing, given that these two technologies are usually regarded as one and the same. The characteristics of firms that use one or the other, however, differ markedly, and these differences also include knowledge depth and scope.

The three last rows of *Table 6* and *7* provide measures of fitness of the estimation. The F-test indicates that the independent variables together differ significantly from zero in all

estimations. The pseudo r^2 measure indicates appropriate levels of fitness. Pseudo r^2 measures are usually lower than the r^2 from ordinary least square regressions.

Robustness

We check the robustness of our results in two ways. First, to detect collinearity, a table of the correlations between different variables used in the analysis is presented in the annex. All correlations between independent variables have acceptable low levels (below 0.3) which follows the recommendation of Hair et al. (2006) supporting that multicollinearity should not be an issue in the analyses. In addition, we apply variance inflation factor (VIF) as a measure of the correlation and strength of correlation between the explanatory variables in a regression model. Here, result for *lemp* indicate potentially a potential correlation with other explanatory variables in the model. To examine the potential effect on our result we exclude *lemp* and re-run the models. The results reveal that the same variables as in our unchanged models are also significant in the models without *lemp*, so there is no negative effect of collinearity on the results.

Second, Germany, the largest economy in Europe, is the country with the largest number of observations in the sample (1,174). To assure that the results are not driven by German manufacturing practices, we further ran the models without Germany. The results are in the main effects unchanged. Finally, adding to the sensitivity analyses, we test the hypotheses with respect to the use of AMT in general, and then subsequently test the effects for its different applications (rapid prototyping, additive manufacturing, and both simultaneously). As the literature does not provide sufficient basis to develop substantial hypotheses, we present the findings for the AMT variable first and then the results for the single purposes of the technology use subsequently. In this way, we can both test the main hypotheses and further develop insights for theory development.

DISCUSSION

AMT and Innovation

This article finds support for AMT being positively related to manufacturing firms' likelihood of product innovation – both incremental and radical product innovation. Hence, the adoption of AMT enables the firm to both realize more innovative opportunities and with higher market novelty (*Hypothesis 1*). Empirically, we ensured that the AMT investments precedes the innovation activities due to the exclusion of cases of adoption of AMT in the innovation period (2012 to 2015). AMT is hence not just another manufacturing technology, but can improve both innovative output as well as the innovation process itself; an *invention of a method of invention* just like e.g. artificial intelligence (Cockburn et al., 2017). This study thereby responds to the call for empirical validation of the positive impact of AMT on manufacturing firms' product innovation activities (e.g., Floriane et al. 2016; Perez et al., 2019; Sauerwein et al., 2019; Rosenzweig & Mazursky, 2014; Petralia, 2020).

Diving further into the exploration of the purpose of the AMT, we find that increases of firms' product innovation can be observed when rapid prototyping and additive manufacturing are applied simultaneously. As previous studies on AMT were not able to differentiate between different types of product novelty and various AMT applications along the product development process (like rapid prototyping and additive manufacturing) (Zhao et al., 2020; Niaki et al., 2019), our results provide novel insights for innovation and technology management research. The findings support that AMT is a multi-purpose technology which yields complementary effects when applied simultaneously in different functional areas of the firm (Savolainen and Collan 2020;

Marion and Fixson 2020; Petralia 2020). These results further accentuate the need for increasing cross-departmental and cross-functional mechanisms for knowledge integration as AMT transverses the formerly separated stages of product development and manufacturing. Hence, cross-pollination facilitated by technology adoption and use across departmental silos may break down knowledge sharing barriers and stimulate creativity for further innovation and performance. These findings are in line with previous literature emphasizing the multi-purpose nature of AMT and its implications on interdisciplinary and cross-departmental processes as well as general synergies between the proximity of R&D and manufacturing activities (Castellani & Lavoratori, 2020; Ketokivi & Ali-Yrkkö, 2009).

In this way, we observe that AMT blurs the lines between the formerly separated stages of product development, product design and product engineering in line literature on digital innovation (Lanzolla et al., 2021; Appio et al., 2021), which projects that digital technologies have the power to change innovation processes and even innovation management. For analytical comparison, the effects of AMT on innovation are similar to the changes ascribed to artificial intelligence (Cockburn et al. 2017, Haefner et al. 2021):

Where AI drives the front-end of innovation (Kakatkar, Bilgram, & Füller, 2020), the largest effects of AMT are more manifested in the downstream stages of the innovation process (as shown above), when firms transfer new ideas into workable artefacts or adapt products to changes in consumers' preferences. AI allows firms to identify and evaluate more information, recognize more problems and opportunities, and generate more ideas based on the data than any other known method in innovation management. The search process for new ideas and concepts may then become less dependent on the knowledge and the competencies of specialized scientific personnel and more capital-intensive as Big Data gets organized for innovation (Lanzolla et al., 2021). AMT enables

experimentation and makes the creation of models of new products much easier than with wood or clay. A pre-condition to fully benefit from AMT, however, are highly integrated production processes so that changes in design can seamlessly be integrated in new products. For innovation management, these results imply that if the firm is blocked in the front-end and more knowledge is needed then AI may be the way forward (Mikalef, Boura, Lekakos, & Krogstie, 2019). When the firm seeks to exploit the opportunities of physical objects across projects, teams, and even organizational boundaries, AMT may serve as a mechanism to knowledge sharing and teamwork. While both AI and AMT are digital technologies, the illustrated process changes call for further research that both investigates specific technologies and combine these to understand, how to orchestrate future digital technology portfolios for innovation performance. Furthermore, as AI requires strong IT skills, AMT requires a combination of depth and scope for innovation. Hence, then the recommendation is to create the right depth and scope of prior knowledge to close interactions between design and production. In any case, either of these digital technologies call for investments to digitally connect all internal enterprise functions, in particular production, with the more upstream stages. On the other hand, it may also call for a joint location of design, product development, and production, which has been abandoned by many firms favoring geographically dispersed locations to benefit from locational advantages. A further complication for innovation managers is that while skills at the graduate level supports radical innovation, the results also highlighted that for AMT secondary upper education is needed. Hence, the right set of skills to adopt and benefit from digital technologies are interwoven and not easily defined. A final consequence from a blurring boundary between production and design due to AMT may be less specialization of the staff and more mobility between different enterprise functions. If AMT reduces the requirements for special skills needed for design, firms may bring

design closer to employees that are in contact with customers, or even to the customer itself.

The role of prior knowledge as an enabler of AMT

Given the positive relationship of AMT usage on firms' product innovation activities, the core research gap as formulated by Paiola et al. (2021) and Steenhuis and Pretorius (2016) appear even more urgent and led to the formulation of the research question: *To what extent do characteristics of the firm's prior knowledge support the adoption of additive manufacturing technologies for product innovation?*

Our results widely confirm the conceptual reasoning underlying *Hypotheses 2 and 3* as they confirm that both depth and scope of firms' prior knowledge represent important strategic resources for the adoption of digital technologies such as AMT.

Specifically, the depth of prior knowledge on the individual level underpins the role of firms' formal education base (Da Silva & Davis, 2011; Knudsen & Schleimer, 2020; Katila & Ahuja, 2002; Zhou & Li, 2012; Caner & Tyler, 2015; Horvat et al., 2019). The depth of prior knowledge held by employees is a decisive characteristic for the adoption of AMT in general, and for rapid prototyping in particular (*Hypothesis 2*). On the organizational level, the performance of R&D activities as a reflection of the depth of prior knowledge increases the likelihood of AMT adoption, which is fully in line with Cohen and Levinthal (1990). Consequently, the findings imply that a higher depth of prior knowledge is associated to R&D and/or technology-intensive firms with focusing on product innovation and now digital innovation particularly through rapid prototyping. One reason can be that rapid prototyping allows for quick and iterative experimenting and testing of product designs.

For the adoption of AMT in manufacturing, however, the share of employees holding a tertiary degree is insignificant for AMT adoption. Instead, it is the share of employees with upper secondary education, so people who are working from a stronger practice-based approach rather than science-based approaches, who positively makes the difference. While this appears reasonable, it underlines the need for applying a differentiated view on skills and knowledge as characteristics of the knowledge-base when examining digital technologies for innovation. Therefore, innovation and technology managers should be aware that different types and carriers of prior knowledge differently support the adoption of AMT applications.

Our results prove equally that the scope of firms' prior knowledge increases the probability of successful AMT adoption (*Hypothesis 3*). Supporting previous studies by Caner and Tyler (2015) and Ahuja and Katila (2002), we show that a higher digital maturity of firms' yields complementarities for AMT adoption (Geissbauer, Vedso, and Schrauf 2016; Klötzer and Pflaum 2017; Schumacher, Erol, and Sihm 2016). Hence, AMT adoption profits when being embedded into a mature digital environment comprehending digital document management systems, CAD-CAM systems for designing, engineering, and executing the manufacturing of digital 3D-layered models (Holmström et al., 2016; Chanias & Hess, 2016). Surprisingly, the firms' digital maturity shows relevance for the adoption of rapid prototyping, while it is not positively correlated with the adoption of AMT for manufacturing purposes. It might be reasoned that AMT for manufacturing purposes comes with a higher disruptive potential, representing a manufacturing paradigm in its own (Hopkinson et al., 2016). Thus, AMT in manufacturing might be less tied to prior knowledge as the knowledge is coming from adopting and using other digital technologies. In contrast, AMT for rapid prototyping could be rather seen as an instrument or tool to enhance prior knowledge in product development and design. But perhaps this

only means that companies in the survey have not yet realized the full potential for radically changed product design offered by AMT (Rindfleisch, O'Hern, and Sachdev 2017; Meier et al. 2019).

To summarize, the results clearly imply that rapid prototyping and additive manufacturing, despite both belonging to the family of AMT, are in many ways two distinct application areas. Consequently, the adoption of different AMT applications is interlinked with different characteristics of firms' prior knowledge base. For innovation and technology managers these findings, on the one hand, strongly suggests that building for preparing the firm with prior knowledge is important when considering adopting AMT, which is in line with Tanaka and Masuda (2020) and Andriani and Kaminska (2021). On the other hand, when it comes to the choice and investment decision related to AMT, managers should be well-aware to ensure the best possible strategic fit between the prior knowledge base and the potential knowledge application domain with the purpose of use (RP vs manufacturing). AMT has the potential to support firm's constant strive to stay and become even more innovative, while also supporting the change in digitalizing the innovation process itself. Bear in mind though that smaller firms are less likely to adopt AMT for rapid prototyping and adoption is fairly limited by the smallest of the firms. At the same time, these firms are simultaneously more likely to use AMT for additive manufacturing processes. While it is well-known that small and medium sized firms (SME's) are less innovative (Andries & Czarnitzki, 2014; de Jong & Vermeulen, 2006; Laforet, 2009) and struggle to convert from being less innovative to increase their innovativeness (Frenz & Prevezer, 2012), these results suggest that firm characteristics (next to their knowledge base) are important for understanding adoption of digital technologies and therefore to enhance our understanding of the complexities of digital innovation.

CONCLUSIONS AND FURTHER IMPLICATIONS

This article makes a strong contribution to the innovation management research with insights also for the literature on technology acceptance by introducing and empirically validating the relevance of several characteristics of the firm's knowledge base as a strategic resource for technology adoption. Taken from the detailed results and the discussion, it is shown that AMT has the potential to both reinvent the innovation process and lead to innovation. In this way, this article confirms that AMT is a special kind of technology which, to some extent, comes along with its own principles and mechanisms.

Additional contextual effects relating to size are noticeable, which implies that recommendations for managers should be separated for SMEs and larger firms. Specifically, managers of SME's can benefit from the finding that additive manufacturing does not profit from prior digital technological knowledge and therefore the typical low resource SME can leap forward by adopting and securing the benefits from AMT. In practical terms, it is less important what purposes the AMT are being applied to – what matters is that printers are made available to the employees to experiment and probe for innovative opportunities. This is concluded as the share of innovators is higher among users of rapid prototyping application as well as among simultaneous users of both AMT applications compared to users of additive manufacturing applications. As the results also show, non-adopters are also less innovative, so the potential for harvesting the benefits from adopting AMT is most likely higher for innovative firms that have not yet adopted the technology, but awareness around these findings should enable the managerial team to prioritize future investments.

Digitalization is currently being researched heavily and especially the literature on digital transformation is growing rapidly, while digital innovation is increasingly also in focus. While this article finds direct effects of the firm's digitalization effort on innovation, it further shows that digitalization supports adoption of AMT in general and for rapid prototyping, in particular. Furthermore, the strongest adoption factor is secondary-upper education, which is characterized by being highly capable employees, who thrive with hands-on and doing-using-interacting rather than highly skilled employees with tertiary education, who are needed for innovation and for radical innovation, in particular. Therefore, we argue and urge firms to take care that there is no hollowing-out of the employee group with secondary upper educations as these are instrumental in benefitting from AMT and most likely other digital technologies. A final word of caution is that these results suggest that firms may in the course of digital transformation, result with a digital divide between low-skilled and high-skilled employees.

LIMITATIONS

As with every study, this analysis is not without limitations. It uses a large sample of European firms but is limited to the years before 2015. Any recent uptakes in adoption patterns are therefore not captured by the current study. The adopters of AMT in the sample may therefore predominantly be early movers in the technology. Future studies should enlarge the samples to the years after 2015. Moreover, since prices for AMT has dropped considerably in the last years and the technology has become increasingly affordable for smaller firms, such an update will potentially influence the discussion of the contextual variables and should therefore explicitly seek to validate these. While the current study has given substantial insight into the link between AMT, the use in different domains and innovation, the study has not been able to provide insights into potential

mechanisms between AMT and innovation. Ideally future research designs should build data that would allow for researching these mechanisms.

The different use cases of AMT, whether for RP or for MM or in the future mass customization and how these may require specialized capabilities and potentially managerial mechanisms to connect and benefit, require further research. Finally, in-depth qualitative studies and comparative studies outside the European Union could provide a more thorough understanding of the required knowledge, capabilities, and organizational practices to put AMT to best use in firms.

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Table 1: Variables used in the multivariate analysis

Type	Variable	Description	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
	amt	Any type of AM used	0.12	0.32	0	1
Dependent variables	only_p	AM only for prototyping	0.04	0.21	0	1
	only_m	AM only for additive manufacturing	0.05	0.21	0	1
	both	AM used for both	0.02	0.16	0	1
	innov	Introduction of new products	0.58	0.49	0	1
	Radical	Introduction of market novelties	0.26	0.44	0	1
Independent variables	lemp	Number of employees, log	4.34	1.02	3.00	10.28
	RD	Research and development	0.47	0.50	0	1
	skill_1	Share of tertiary graduates	0.09	0.11	0	0.9
	skill_2	Share of upper secnd. graduates	0.12	0.14	0	1
	digindex	Index of digitalization	1.07	1.34	0	5
	export	Share of exports on turnover	35.12	34.53	0	100
	consumer	The firm supplies to consumers	0.27	0.44	0	1
	s_cus	Customers as a source for ideas for innovation	0.76	0.43	0	1
	s_sup	Suppliers as a source for ideas for innovation	0.15	0.36	0	1
Industry variables	fb	Food and beverages	0.11	0.31	0	1
	tex	Textiles, clothing, leather	0.04	0.19	0	1
	wood	Wood, pulp and paper	0.10	0.29	0	1
	chem	Chemicals, pharmaceuticals	0.06	0.23	0	1
	plast	Plastics	0.06	0.24	0	1
	glass	Glass, cements, bricks, etc	0.05	0.22	0	1

	metal	Metals and metal products	0.20	0.40	0	1
	computer	Computers, telecom equip.	0.07	0.25	0	1
	electrical	Electrical equipment	0.05	0.22	0	1
	mach	Machinery	0.14	0.35	0	1
	vehk	Vehicles	0.03	0.17	0	1
	other	Other manufacturing	0.06	0.23	0	1

Figure 1: Diffusion of AMT, 1995-2015

EMS, own calculations

Table 2: Diffusion of AM: experience, size and high-skilled employees, 2015

Type	Share	No. of employees (mean)	Experience (years)	High-skilled employees (mean)	Impulses from customers
no AMT	87.8%	150	-	20.4%	75%
only rapid prototyping	4.7%	448	8.0	27.3%	75%
only additive manufacturing	5.0%	108	17.5	27.4%	84%
both types of AMT	2.6%	546	12.5	27.9%	81%

EMS, own calculations

Table 3: Diffusion of AM and firm size, 2015

Type	< 50 employees (share)	50-249 employees (share)	250-999 employees (share)	+1000 employees (share)
only rapid prototyping	2%	5%	10%	22%
only additive manufacturing	6%	5%	4%	2%
both types of AMT	2%	3%	3%	14%

EMS, own calculations

Table 4: Diffusion of AM at the level of industries, 2015

Industry	no AMT	Only rapid prototyping	only additive manufacturing	both types of AMT
Food, beverages	97%	0%	3%	0%
Tex, cloth, leather	94%	1%	3%	2%
Wood, paper, print	91%	2%	6%	1%
Pharma, chemicals	93%	2%	4%	1%
plastic	83%	6%	6%	5%
Mineral prod.	92%	3%	3%	2%
Metal	87%	5%	6%	2%
Computer	79%	9%	7%	5%
Electrical	79%	12%	5%	4%
Machinery	87%	7%	3%	3%
Vehicles	80%	5%	7%	8%
Other	80%	7%	8%	5%

EMS, own calculations

Table 5: Diffusion of AM and innovation, 2015

Type	Product innovators (share)	Length of innovation process (months)	Radical innovators (share)	Firms with R&D (share)
no AMT	56%	16.2	25%	44%
only rapid prototyping	77%	21.2	49%	75%
only additive manufacturing	69%	18.9	32%	44%
both types of AMT	81%	20.2	51%	73%

EMS, own calculations

Table 6: Innovation and additive manufacturing

VARIABLES	(1) innov	(2) radical
only_p	0.087** (0.042)	0.105** (0.045)
only_m	0.129*** (0.040)	0.092** (0.045)
both	0.136** (0.061)	0.180*** (0.064)
lemp	0.022* (0.012)	0.025** (0.010)
RD	0.250*** (0.021)	0.191*** (0.019)
skill_1	0.202* (0.106)	0.227*** (0.087)
skill_2	0.074 (0.079)	0.036 (0.071)
digindex	0.028*** (0.008)	0.013* (0.007)
export	0.001*** (0.000)	0.001*** (0.000)
consumer	0.054** (0.025)	0.031 (0.024)
s_cus	0.038 (0.024)	0.004 (0.022)
s_sup	-0.014 (0.029)	-0.033 (0.025)
tex	0.015 (0.060)	0.077 (0.060)
wood	-0.014 (0.044)	-0.009 (0.040)
chem	-0.027 (0.053)	-0.087** (0.039)
plast	-0.042 (0.051)	-0.005 (0.045)
glass	-0.063 (0.054)	0.012 (0.049)
metal	-0.133*** (0.041)	-0.089*** (0.033)
computer	0.050 (0.053)	0.001 (0.047)
electrical	0.014 (0.056)	-0.038 (0.046)
mach	0.071* (0.042)	0.024 (0.040)
vehk	-0.079 (0.067)	-0.046 (0.053)
other	-0.087* (0.052)	-0.080** (0.040)
Observations	2,641	2,646
F-test/prob >	0.0000	0.0000
chi2	475.2	333.2
Pseudo r2	0.134	0.105

Standard errors in parentheses*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * <0.1

EMS, own calculations

Table 7: Determinants of the use of additive manufacturing

VARIABLES	(1) Any type of AM	(2) Only rapid prototyping	(3) Only additive manufacturing	(4) Both types
lemp	0.018*** (0.006)	0.004*** (0.001)	-0.010** (0.004)	0.002 (0.002)
RD	0.050*** (0.013)	0.008*** (0.002)	-0.001 (0.008)	0.013*** (0.004)
skill_1	-0.043 (0.059)	-0.005 (0.008)	-0.025 (0.038)	0.003 (0.016)
skill_2	0.132*** (0.042)	0.013** (0.006)	0.047* (0.025)	0.012 (0.011)
digindex	0.022*** (0.004)	0.001** (0.001)	0.004 (0.003)	0.006*** (0.001)
export	0.000 (0.000)	0.000** (0.000)	0.000 (0.000)	-0.000 (0.000)
consumer	-0.008 (0.016)	0.001 (0.002)	-0.015* (0.009)	0.005 (0.005)
s_cus	0.004 (0.014)	-0.005* (0.003)	0.017** (0.008)	0.001 (0.004)
s_sup	-0.004 (0.017)	-0.002 (0.002)	0.004 (0.011)	-0.000 (0.005)
tex	0.057 (0.064)	0.992*** (0.007)	-0.006 (0.024)	0.053 (0.056)
wood	0.137** (0.055)	0.995*** (0.003)	0.039 (0.029)	0.002 (0.017)
chem	0.042 (0.050)	0.986*** (0.002)	0.017 (0.028)	0.016 (0.027)
plast	0.283*** (0.070)	0.998*** (0.001)	0.046 (0.033)	0.120 (0.073)
glass	0.109* (0.062)	0.996*** (0.002)	-0.001 (0.023)	0.043 (0.045)
metal	0.174*** (0.049)	0.989*** (0.006)	0.029 (0.023)	0.043 (0.031)
computer	0.249*** (0.070)	0.997*** (0.001)	0.055 (0.038)	0.060 (0.050)
electrical	0.266*** (0.073)	0.997*** (0.001)	0.018 (0.029)	0.062 (0.053)
mach	0.139*** (0.051)	0.994*** (0.004)	-0.001 (0.019)	0.055 (0.040)
vehk	0.262*** (0.083)	0.995*** (0.002)	0.059 (0.047)	0.141 (0.091)
other	0.291*** (0.070)	0.997*** (0.001)	0.063* (0.037)	0.111 (0.070)
Observations	2,646	2,646	2,646	2,646
F-test/prob >	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
chi2	235.2	183.3	93.26	108.5
Pseudo r2	0.116	0.173	0.0860	0.170

Standard errors in parentheses*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * <0.1

EMS, own calculations